

Supplementary Material for: “Because Microchips are the Future:” Investigating End Users’ Information Needs Regarding Microchips

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Abstract

In the context of the publication “‘Because Microchips are the Future:’ Investigating End Users’ Information Needs Regarding Microchips”, we conducted an online survey with 250 participants recruited via Prolific. This supplementary material gives a rationale for the survey design and provides a transcript of the survey itself. Parts of the survey are also used in another publication, which has not yet been published.

1. Survey Description

A core part of the survey is a vignette setup: to make the concept of microchips less abstract and more accessible, we presented the participants with five scenarios based on real-world applications of microchips. Each vignette consisted of a setting that describes a particular use case of a microchip and a desideratum (i. e., a property that might be desirable to end users). Following the vignette description, we asked participants to rate the importance of the desideratum as well as the importance of receiving specific types of information about the microchip in the respective scenario. Below, we outline our rationale for selecting vignette components and information types, present details of questionnaire design and study procedures, and address ethical considerations and data analysis techniques.

1.1. Topic Selection and Item Generation

As the first step of scoping the survey, we identified five concrete settings in which microchips may be used,

five desiderata that end users may want satisfied for microchips, and five kinds of information presented to end users. The settings, desiderata, and information types were derived from a literature review and discussions among experts, and refined in pilot studies (see Section 1.3).

Derivation of settings involving microchips To help end users relate to microchips, we selected five settings in which microchips are employed. We deliberately selected settings across a diverse range of applications, touching on aspects that end users may encounter in their everyday lives. Specifically, we consider microchips (i) *controlling the entertainment system in a car*, (ii) *enabling wireless communication in a cell tower*, (iii) *controlling a pacemaker to maintain an adequate heart rate*, (iv) *enabling fingerprint unlocking of a smartphone*, and (v) *controlling the steering of an airplane*.

Derivation of end-user desiderata In our survey, we consider different goals that are desirable for end users. We borrow an initial set of desiderata from literature on other technical systems (Chazette et al., 2021; Langer et al., 2021; Speith, 2023). Through pilot testing (see Section 1.3), we narrowed down the selection to five desiderata that are relevant for microchips and at the same time relatable to end users: (a) *accountability*, (b) *safety*, (c) *cyber security*, (d) *trustworthiness*, and (e) *ethical standards*. For each desiderata, the following definitions have been provided to the participants:

- **Accountability** means being able to find out who is at fault when something goes wrong with a

microchip. If there is a failure, it is important to know who is responsible so they can provide proper compensation.

- **Safety** means ensuring that devices with microchips do not harm their surroundings or people. If a microchip malfunctions, it could cause the system to fail and result in physical damage or injuries.
- **Cyber security** means safeguarding the microchips we use from unauthorized access by individuals or organizations. If the microchips are not secure, it could result in confidential information being stolen, altered, or deleted.
- **Trustworthiness** means that the microchips we use not only function as intended but can even demonstrate that they do so. If a microchip behaves as it should but fails to convince us that it does so, it would not be considered trustworthy.
- **Ethical standards** mean that the microchips we use have been produced in a responsible manner. This includes fair treatment and compensation of employees and sustainable use of resources.

Derivation of information facilitating microchip understanding The five different kinds of information offered to the end user are derived from different stages of the microchip design and manufacturing process (Lienig and Scheible, 2020; Weste and Harris, 2015). Microchips are designed using a high-level language similar to regular programming languages. The design descriptions are then implemented as an electronic circuit using automated software tools. Next, the design is handed to the manufacturer who produces the microchip in one of their production facilities, also known as *fabs* (Geiger et al., 1990). Derived from this process, we list the following as information to provide about microchips: (1) *who designed and manufactured the microchips* and (2) *how the microchips were designed and manufactured*.

Especially safety- and security-critical microchips must be certified by independent government bodies or dedicated testing service providers before use. As such, another useful piece of information could be (3) *how the microchips have been approved for use*.

The fabricated chip is finally integrated into a device such as a smartphone, a pacemaker, or a car. Therefore, further relevant information could be (4) *how the microchips interact with the system* and (5) *which functionality the microchips provide*.

1.2. Questionnaire Design

We drew from our team members' expertise in usable security and embedded systems when designing the questionnaire. We took care to make our questionnaire understandable to end users through several rounds of piloting. In the following, we briefly describe the flow of our questionnaire (see Section 2 for a full version).

1.2.1. Introduction At the beginning, we stated the purpose of our study, the expected duration of 25 minutes, and provided information on data handling and data protection. Before participants could proceed, we asked them to give informed consent and to confirm that they were residents of the United States and at least 18 years of age (Q 1). Next, we asked participants nine questions on a six-point Likert scale to assess their tendency to actively engage in technology interaction (Q2) using a validated psychometric scale (Franke et al., 2019).

1.2.2. General questions on microchips In an open question, we asked participants what comes to mind when thinking of microchips (Q 3). Further, we asked them whether or not they would like to understand more about microchips and invited them to give reasons for their choice (Q 4). We also queried participants regarding the time they would be willing to invest to better understand microchips (Q 5) and on the time they currently invest for the same purpose (Q 6), both on a five-point scale. Next, we provided some background on microchips to align participants' basic understanding (Q 7). To conclude this block, we presented five settings in randomized order involving microchips and asked participants to rate their criticality as the impact that a microchip malfunction would have on the participant themselves (Q8).

1.2.3. Vignettes From the 25 possible combinations of settings and desiderata (see Section 1.1), we formed five sets of five vignettes each, in which each setting and each desideratum occurs only exactly once. At the core of our questionnaire, we showed participants one of these sets. An example vignette is shown in Q 10. For each vignette, we first asked participants to rate the importance of having a high level of the respective desideratum in the setting at hand on a five-point Likert scale (Q 10.1). We then invited participants to explain their choices in an open-ended response (Q 10.2). Second, we asked participants to rate the importance of receiving each of the five types of information (see Section 1.1) to assess the given desideratum in the

specified setting on a five-point Likert scale (Q 10.3). Subsequently, we requested them to briefly explain their choice for one of the information types in an open-ended response (Q 10.4). Throughout the vignettes, we provided tooltips for some phrases (see **red** parts in Q 10) that, once hovered over with the cursor, would explain desiderata and types of information in simple language so that participants' mental models of these items are aligned to our understanding and they could get clarifications as needed as they completed the survey.

1.2.4. Comprehension check To determine whether participants actually understood the desiderata, we presented them with an assignment exercise that asked them to match five randomly ordered sentences indicating the meaning of a desideratum to the desideratum in question (Q 11). The content of the sentences was based on the tooltips for the desiderata from the vignettes. We again asked participants about their willingness to invest time in understanding microchips (Q 12) to see whether it has changed compared to before (Q 5).

1.2.5. Demographics We asked for participants to indicate their gender (Q 13), age range (Q 14), highest level of education (Q 15), and whether they had any prior practical experience with microchips (Q 16). Finally, we inquired if our participants had any feedback or anything they would like to share with us (Q 17).

1.3. Survey Implementation

We implemented our questionnaire using Qualtrics and recruited US-based English-speaking participants via Prolific.

1.3.1. Pilot Testing We conducted several pilot studies with a total of 79 participants to ensure end-user comprehension—specifically of the desiderata—by analyzing the open-ended questions Q 10.2 and Q 10.4 on participants' assessment of Q 10.1 and Q 10.3 with respect to misunderstandings. Through these pilots, we aimed to determine whether our desiderata are indeed relevant to and comprehensible for end users, and if we had missed any desiderata that were important to them. The extensive piloting led to several iterations of the questionnaire, particularly in terms of wording, sharpening of information types, and exclusion of unclear or irrelevant desiderata.

1.3.2. Data Collection We rolled out the main study with a gender-balanced sample of 250 participants over 10 days by releasing slots to batches of 25 participants,

each at different times of the day. The sample size of 250 was determined using a power analysis for multiple regression models. We aimed for the detection of a small effect size $f^2=0.15$, power=0.95, and a significance level of $\alpha=0.05$. For our power analysis, we indicated a total of 27 predictors, which is the sum of the number of vignettes, one's affinity for technology interaction (ATI) score (see Q 2; Franke et al., 2019) and whether or not participants would like to understand more about microchips (see Q4). Participants took a median time of 24:19 minutes to complete our questionnaire and were compensated with 7.50 GBP, thus an hourly wage of 18.51 GBP.

1.4. Ethics and Data Protection

We could not have our planned study fully reviewed by an ethics committee because our department did not operate an institutional review board (IRB) at the time. However, we reviewed our study in line with the application form for ethical approval of human studies from another department and reached the conclusion that our study would be IRB-exempt in their case. In addition, by limiting the survey to a few demographic questions, notably not asking about region of residence, we ensured the anonymity of our participants from the beginning. All data collected were stored on our institution's own servers, to which only the researchers involved in the project have access.

2. Survey Material

This section provides the verbatim survey as it was presented to our 250 end-user participants.

2.1. Your Perspective on Microchips

- (1) Thank you for your interest in our study!

Purpose: Increasing digitalization in all areas of life is being driven by the constantly rising performance and efficiency of microchips. With this survey, we would like to learn more about the desired goals of end users regarding their understanding of microchips, and how these goals may be achieved. By faithfully completing this survey, you can help make microchips more understandable to end users in the future.

Duration: Participation in the study is expected to take a maximum of 25 minutes. You are not subject to any anticipated risks by participating. Please answer the survey as honestly as possible. You may stop at any time if you no longer wish to participate in the study. In case you drop out

of the study, all responses recorded so far will be discarded.

Data Privacy Statement & Informed Consent:

Your responses to this study are stored in anonymized form in a way which will not reveal your identity. No data will be passed on to third parties. By starting this questionnaire you consent to data collection for the purposes of conducting this study. Your personal data is processed based on Article 6 (1) a GDPR and *[redacted for review]*. You have the right to revoke your consent to the data processing at any time as well as to request information, correction, processing restrictions and deletion of the data stored about you. To exercise these rights, please contact the email address listed below. The responsible supervisory authority is the *[redacted]*. If you have additional questions about data protection, please contact *[redacted]*.

To participate, you must be 18 years of age or older and a resident of the United States.

- (1.1) I am 18 years of age or older. Yes No
- (1.2) I am a resident of the United States. Yes No
- (1.3) I confirm that I accept the participation conditions for this study. Yes No
- (1.4) I do not agree and don't want to participate. Yes No

2.2. Your Interaction with Technical Systems

- (2) In the following questionnaire, we will ask you about your **interaction with technical systems**. The term '**technical systems**' refers to apps and other **software applications**, as well as entire **digital devices** (e.g. mobile phone, computer, TV, car navigation).

Please indicate the **degree** to which you **agree/disagree** with the following statements.

- (2.1) I like to occupy myself in greater detail with technical systems. completely disagree largely disagree slightly disagree slightly agree largely agree completely agree
- (2.2) I like testing the functions of new technical systems. completely disagree largely disagree slightly disagree slightly agree largely agree completely agree
- (2.3) I predominantly deal with technical systems because I have to. completely disagree largely disagree slightly disagree

- slightly agree largely agree completely agree

- (2.4) When I have a new technical system in front of me, I try it out intensively. completely disagree largely disagree slightly disagree slightly agree largely agree completely agree
- (2.5) I enjoy spending time becoming acquainted with a new technical system. completely disagree largely disagree slightly disagree slightly agree largely agree completely agree
- (2.6) It is enough for me that a technical system works; I don't care how or why. completely disagree largely disagree slightly disagree slightly agree largely agree completely agree
- (2.7) I try to understand how a technical system exactly works. completely disagree largely disagree slightly disagree slightly agree largely agree completely agree
- (2.8) It is enough for me to know the basic functions of a technical system. completely disagree largely disagree slightly disagree slightly agree largely agree completely agree
- (2.9) I try to make full use of the capabilities of a technical system. completely disagree largely disagree slightly disagree slightly agree largely agree completely agree

2.3. Microchip Understanding

- (3) What comes to your mind when you think of **microchips**, also known as "computer chips" and "integrated circuits"? Please take a minute to think about the question and write down everything that comes to your mind. *[free text]*
- (4) Would **you personally** like to understand more about **microchips**? Yes, because ... *[free text]* No, because ... *[free text]*
- (5) How much time would you **be willing** to invest **per newly acquired device** to better understand the **microchips** it contains? less than 1 hour 1 to less than 2 hours 2 to less than 3 hours 3 to less than 4 hours 4 or more hours
- (6) How much time do you **currently** invest **per newly acquired device** to better understand the **microchips** it contains? less than 1 hour 1 to

less than 2 hours 2 to less than 3 hours 3 to less than 4 hours 4 or more hours

2.4. A Brief Background on Microchips

- (7) Microchips are tiny objects that store and operate on information in the form of digital data. They are a crucial part of many electronic devices we use every day, like phones, cars, planes, medical implants, and industrial systems. Microchips play a major role in the development of digital technology and make advanced applications like artificial intelligence possible. These chips are highly complex, they are composed of extremely small structures, and are made in various facilities around the world.

2.5. Criticality of Use Cases

- (8) On a scale from 1—not at all critical to 5—extremely critical, how critical do you **personally** consider the following **microchip use cases**. Think about the impact a malfunctioning or failing microchip has **on you** in each particular use case.
- (8.1) You are a passenger in an **airplane** that contains **microchips to control its steering**.
 1—not at all critical 2—slightly critical
 3—moderately critical 4—very critical
 5—extremely critical
- (8.2) You are driving in a **car** that contains **microchips to control its entertainment system**.
 1—not at all critical
 2—slightly critical 3—moderately critical
 4—very critical 5—extremely critical
- (8.3) You use a **smartphone** that contains **microchips enabling fingerprint unlocking**.
 1—not at all critical
 2—slightly critical 3—moderately critical
 4—very critical 5—extremely critical
- (8.4) You are making a call through a **cell tower** that relies on **microchips for wireless communication**.
 1—not at all critical
 2—slightly critical 3—moderately critical
 4—very critical 5—extremely critical
- (8.5) You have a **pacemaker** implanted that contains **microchips to maintain an adequate heart rate**.
 1—not at all critical
 2—slightly critical 3—moderately

critical 4—very critical 5—extremely critical

2.6. Vignettes

- (9) Next, we will show you five different scenarios of devices containing microchips and ask you to answer a few questions for each scenario.

Please read the descriptions of each scenario carefully and answer the questions thoughtfully.

(10) Scenario x/5

Please imagine **yourself** being in the following situation:

You are a passenger in an **airplane** that contains microchips to **control its steering**.

Think about the **safety implications** of these microchips. Safety means keeping yourself and the system safe from physical harm.

① By hovering over a word marked in red, you can get more information on the respective term.

- (10.1) On a scale from 1—not at all important to 5—extremely **important**, how important is it to you **personally** to have a high level of **safety** for **microchips controlling the steering of an airplane**?

① When rating the importance of safety in this scenario, you could think about the following questions: Is it relevant to you? Would you care about it?
 1—not at all important 2—slightly important
 3—moderately important 4—very important
 5—extremely important

- (10.2) Please briefly explain why you rated the importance of **safety** to you in this scenario as you did. *[free text]*

- (10.3) On a scale from 1—not at all important to 5—extremely important, how **important** is it to you **personally** to receive the following **information** for assessing the **safety** of microchips controlling the steering of an airplane?

① When rating the importance of information, you could think about the following questions: Could such information provide any benefit to you? Would they be helpful for you to evaluate the safety?

- (10.3.1) Information about **who designed and manufactured the microchips**.
 1—not at all important 2—slightly important
 3—moderately important

- 4—very important ○ 5—extremely important
- (10.3.2) Information about **how the microchips interact with the system**. ○ 1—not at all important ○ 2—slightly important ○ 3—moderately important ○ 4—very important ○ 5—extremely important
- (10.3.3) Information about **how the microchips have been approved for use**. ○ 1—not at all important ○ 2—slightly important ○ 3—moderately important ○ 4—very important ○ 5—extremely important
- (10.3.4) Information about **which functionality the microchips provide**. ○ 1—not at all important ○ 2—slightly important ○ 3—moderately important ○ 4—very important ○ 5—extremely important
- (10.3.5) Information about **how the microchips were designed and manufactured**. ○ 1—not at all important ○ 2—slightly important ○ 3—moderately important ○ 4—very important ○ 5—extremely important
- (10.4) Please briefly explain why you rated the importance of receiving "information about **who designed and manufactured the microchips**" to you in this scenario as "4—very important".
 - ⓘ By hovering over a word marked in red, you can get more information on the respective term. *[free text]*

2.7. Microchip Properties

- (11) Please assign each **description** on the left to one of the **properties** on the right. There is **one matching description** for each property. If you don't know the assignment, please make a guess.
 - Properties: ○ safety ○ accountability ○ ethical standards ○ cyber security ○ trustworthiness;
 - descriptions: ○ Ensures that microchips do not cause harm to you or the system. ○ Enables figuring out who is responsible in case something goes wrong. ○ Defines practices for responsible treatment of employees and the environment. ○ Makes sure that sensitive information is kept safe from people who are not allowed to see it or change it. ○ Guarantees that a microchip works properly and can also demonstrate this fact.
- (12) Now that you have answered the previous questions, how much time would you **be willing**

to invest **per newly acquired device** to better understand the **microchips** it contains? ○ less than 1 hour ○ 1 to less than 2 hours ○ 2 to less than 3 hours ○ 3 to less than 4 hours ○ 4 or more hours

2.8. Demographics

- (13) What is your **gender**? ○ Male ○ Female ○ Non-binary ○ Describe yourself: *[free text]* ○ I prefer not to answer this question
- (14) What is your **age**? ○ 18-24 ○ 25-34 ○ 35-44 ○ 45-54 ○ 55-64 ○ 65 or older ○ I prefer not to answer this question
- (15) What is your highest level of **education**? ○ High school or equivalent ○ Some college, no degree ○ Associate's degree, occupational ○ Associate's degree, academic ○ Bachelor's degree ○ Master's degree ○ Professional degree ○ Doctoral degree ○ I prefer not to answer this question
- (16) Do you have practical experience with microchips, e.g., from chip design, manufacturing, testing, deployment, or policies in the semiconductor domain? ○ Yes ○ No ○ I prefer not to answer this question

2.9. Feedback

- (17) Is there anything you would like to tell us about this survey? Please give us your feedback. *[free text]*
- (18) We thank you for your time spent taking this survey. Your response has been recorded. Please click the button below to be redirected to Prolific and register your submission.

3. Demographics

Table 1: Demographics of our 250 participants consisting of gender, age, highest level of education, prior practical experience with microchips, and affinity for technology interaction (Franke et al., 2019).

Demographics (n=250)				
Gender	n	%	Education	n %
<i>Male</i>	121	48.4	<i>High school or equivalent</i>	35 14.0
<i>Female</i>	121	48.4	<i>Some college, no degree</i>	54 21.6
<i>Non-binary</i>	8	3.2	<i>Associate's degree, occupational</i>	8 3.2
<i>Describe yourself</i>	0	0.0	<i>Associate's degree, academic</i>	16 6.4
<i>No answer</i>	0	0.0	<i>Bachelor's degree</i>	98 39.2
Age	n	%	<i>Master's degree</i>	31 12.4
<i>18-24</i>	50	20.0	<i>Professional degree</i>	2 0.8
<i>25-34</i>	89	35.6	<i>Doctoral degree</i>	4 1.6
<i>35-44</i>	57	22.8	<i>No answer</i>	2 0.8
<i>45-54</i>	32	12.8	Prior Experience	n %
<i>55-64</i>	15	6.0	<i>Yes</i>	13 5.2
<i>65 or older</i>	7	2.8	<i>No</i>	231 92.4
<i>No answer</i>	0	0.0	<i>No answer</i>	6 2.4
ATI	mean	4.05	sd	0.91

4. Codebooks for Q3 and Q4

Table 2: Codebook with absolute and relative code frequencies for 250 responses to Q3 (“What comes to your mind when you think of **microchips**, also known as ”computer chips” and ”integrated circuits”?”).

code	frequency		code	frequency	
	abs.	rel.		abs.	rel.
computer	104	0.42	circuit	10	0.04
small size	84	0.34	manufacturing challenges	10	0.04
building block that makes things work	83	0.33	foreign manufacturing	9	0.04
used across devices	71	0.28	gaming	9	0.04
technology	54	0.22	political aspects	8	0.03
electronics	50	0.20	AI	8	0.03
phone	47	0.19	circuit board	8	0.03
technological advancement	47	0.19	GPU	8	0.03
data storage	35	0.14	high complexity	8	0.03
microchip composition	35	0.14	tablet	8	0.03
human implant	29	0.12	fear	7	0.03
CPU	28	0.11	health	7	0.03
other named devices	28	0.11	soldering	7	0.03
animal implant	27	0.11	vaccines	6	0.02
data processing	25	0.10	no idea	5	0.02
brain similarity	24	0.10	privacy	5	0.02
processing power	22	0.09	binary values	4	0.02
vehicle	22	0.09	pop culture reference	4	0.02
tracking	18	0.07	security	4	0.02
supply chain issues	18	0.07	authentication	3	0.01
motherboard	17	0.07	economical dependence	3	0.01
diverse functionality	15	0.06	Elon Musk	3	0.01
memory	13	0.05	ethical concerns	3	0.01
companies	12	0.05	flat	3	0.01
computer parts	12	0.05	profitable	3	0.01
control	12	0.05	stock market	3	0.01
communication	11	0.04	internet	2	0.01
conspiracy	11	0.04	toys	2	0.01
societal impact	11	0.04			

Table 3: Codebook with absolute and relative code frequencies for 250 responses to Q4 (“Would **you personally** like to understand more about **microchips**? Yes/No, because ...”).

code	frequency		code	frequency	
	abs.	rel.		abs.	rel.
gain knowledge	96	0.38	application areas	12	0.05
understand functionality	46	0.18	impact on society	10	0.04
omnipresent in daily life	32	0.13	understand manufacturing	10	0.04
no interest	28	0.11	professional needs	9	0.04
incomplete knowledge	24	0.10	satisfied	9	0.04
scientific progress	24	0.10	fear	8	0.03
keep up with progress	20	0.08	informed decision making	7	0.03
operation before knowledge	18	0.07	risk assessment	7	0.03
no need	16	0.06	diagnose issues	6	0.02
using technology	16	0.06	improve productivity	4	0.02
too complicated	15	0.06	improve quality of life	4	0.02
importance for future	14	0.06	explain to others	2	0.01

5. Detailed Results of Multilevel Regression Analysis

Table 4: Multilevel regression analysis, including interactions, based on participants' ratings of the importance of receiving different types of information to evaluate desideratum in a given setting, on a scale from 1—*not at all important* to 5—*extremely important* (see Q 10.3 for an example question presented to participants).

<i>Predictors</i>	which func- tionality Est.	how interacts Est.	how approved Est.	how manu- factured Est.	who manu- factured Est.
intercept: car (setting) × ethical standards (desideratum)	2.87***	2.43***	2.82***	2.71***	2.66***
<i>interactions (baseline=car × ethical standards)</i>					
car × accountability	-0.16	-0.01	-0.21	-0.37	0.00
car × safety	-0.25	0.09	-0.10	-0.33	-0.08
car × trustworthiness	-0.03	0.04	-0.56*	-0.65**	-0.53*
car × cyber security	0.12	0.65**	0.36	-0.03	0.11
smartphone × ethical standards	0.02	0.25	0.37	0.29	0.60*
smartphone × accountability	0.22	0.07	0.06	0.17	-0.06
smartphone × safety	0.18	0.05	-0.04	-0.07	-0.53
smartphone × trustworthiness	0.44	0.13	0.39	0.08	-0.05
smartphone × security	0.32	-0.07	-0.48	-0.40	-0.52
cell tower × ethical standards	-0.11	0.31	0.28	0.39	0.63*
cell tower × accountability	0.24	-0.01	-0.39	-0.62	-0.93*
cell tower × safety	0.47	-0.10	0.27	-0.18	-0.64
cell tower × trustworthiness	0.28	-0.02	0.28	0.12	-0.16
cell tower × security	0.33	-0.35	0.15	-0.19	-0.21
pacemaker × ethical standards	-0.11	0.31	0.28	0.39	0.63*
pacemaker × accountability	0.42	0.67	0.60	0.19	0.25
pacemaker × safety	0.88*	0.49	0.41	0.53	0.16
pacemaker × trustworthiness	0.60	0.67	1.23**	1.23**	1.12**
pacemaker × security	0.47	-0.04	0.10	0.18	0.14
airplane × ethical standards	0.20	0.53*	0.48	0.81**	0.78**
airplane × accountability	0.59	0.67	0.61	0.19	0.25
airplane × safety	0.43	0.01	0.52	-0.38	-0.34
airplane × trustworthiness	0.46	0.31	0.99**	0.34	0.30
airplane × security	0.31	-0.07	-0.22	-0.61	-0.48
desire to understand more about microchips	0.54***	0.63***	0.40*	0.49**	0.41*
ATI score	0.26***	0.27***	0.26**	0.28***	0.26**
marginal R^2	0.177	0.198	0.180	0.189	0.155
conditional R^2	0.465	0.478	0.522	0.571	0.536

* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$

6. Standard Deviation of Importance Ratings

Figure 1 shows the standard deviation of our participants' importance ratings of our desiderata in the considered settings.

	airplane	car	smartphone	cell tower	pacemaker	total
accountability	0.73	1.14	1.46	1.32	0.72	1.34
ethical standards	1.30	1.25	1.18	1.24	1.19	1.27
cyber security	0.71	1.30	1.25	0.71	0.97	1.11
safety	0.40	1.34	1.29	1.21	0.30	1.31
trustworthiness	0.74	1.28	1.04	1.09	0.47	1.18
total	0.90	1.29	1.28	1.23	0.86	

Figure 1: Standard deviation of participants' importance ratings of our desiderata in the considered settings.

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